

Developmental Studies on 250 KVA Indoor K-Rating Transformer for Industrial Plants

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Abstract— In recent years due to increased non-linear loads, the power quality of the supply is affected. It has raised a serious concern on the use of conventional transformers to meet this non-linear load demand, where the life of transformer get reduced by about 50%. K-rating transformers can handle the non-linear loads without increasing the temperature limits within the transformer. Even the distribution losses can be reduced by using K-rating transformer. In this paper, design of a 250 kVA K-rating transformer and validation of total harmonic distortion in the current waveform is presented to handle the nonlinear load in industrial plants.

Keywords— Non-linear loads, total harmonic distortion, power quality, k-rating, efficiency and regulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Solid-state switching elements like Silicon control rectifiers, transistors, capacitors, electronic ballasts welders, Induction heating equipment, PLCs and Solid state controls, solid state motor drives, telecommunications equipment etc. continuously switch on and off, produce non-sinusoidal pattern in the current waveform, result in harmonics. Among these Third and fifth harmonic currents are more dominant [1-2].

The magnitude of the waveform gets altered due to the harmonics getting superimposed on the fundamental waveform which increase the eddy current and stray losses in the transformer and mainly the neutral carries the 3rd harmonic current. Small Harmonic distortion can be observed in the voltage waveform due to the harmonic current flowing through the leakage impedance of transformer.

All the above effect the transformer to operate at higher temperatures. For every 6°C rise in the operating temperature of a transformer, the life of transformer will be reduced by 50% which considerably reduces the efficiency of the transformer. If the over temperature gets high enough or lasts long enough, the transformer will prematurely fail. Some of the indications of harmonics in a transformer include Overheating of neutral conductors and panels, Line voltage distortion, Control equipment disoperation, Equipment failure, fire hazards, Interference on communication lines etc. Harmonics can be eliminated by filtering or cancellation. Filtering of harmonics is done by using harmonic filter. Harmonic cancellation is done by using phase shifting transformers. Currently “Low zero phase sequencing and phase shifting” technique is used in transformers to treat these harmonics.

The core thrust of K-Rated design is not to lower the increased losses but rather to withstand them without

overheating. K-factor is a ratio between the extra losses due to harmonics and the eddy current losses at 50 Hz. K-factor values varies from 1 to 50.

K-factor of 1 is used for linear loads, loads approaching 100% nonlinear or more than 75% THD should incorporate a K-20 rating. When transformers use a K-factor value, they are said to be K-Rated transformers. K-Factor is a measure of current distortion in the load fed to a transformer. Higher the number, the greater the capacity of the transformer to handle high levels of continuous non-linear loads. Generally K-4 rated transformers for computer and other similar loads found in commercial and industrial systems for duty cycles of 80-95%. If the duty cycle is expected to exceed 95%, then K-13 would be needed. A K-13 transformer can accommodate 200% of the harmonic loading of a K-4 rated transformer. K-13 indicates its ability to accommodate 13 times the eddy current losses of an ideal transformer. Study of K-13 involves measuring the component of harmonic current upto 13 harmonic orders namely- 3,5,7,11,13,17,19, 23,25,29,31,35,37. Harmonic order 9,15,21,33 is ignored since they are triplen harmonics and they cancel out. The harmonic currents up to 13th order are significant and beyond 13th order are insignificant and generally K-13 is adopted [3-4].

K-ratings for different percentage of linear and nonlinear loads are shown in table1.

TABLE 1. K-Ratings.

Type	Linear Load	Nonlinear load	Total K-factor
K4	100%	50%	4
K13	100%	100%	13
K20	100%	125%	20
K30	100%	150%	30

A F Zobia presented the theoretical and case study concepts on harmonic level distortions produced by non-linear loads. Also the author discussed various methods to reduce harmonic distortion [5]. D M Said et al. presented the harmonic analysis by simulation, experimental and assessment methods. From the obtained results conclude that the life of transformer decreases due to the increased losses caused by harmonic currents [6]. M S Taci et al. presented the experimental results of active losses in a transformer considering harmonic amplitude, harmonic order, loading factor and loading time [7]. N.R. Jayasinghe et al. Discussed about different design techniques for withstanding the harmonic currents like parallel winding, reduced flux density, using static shields. The obtained results were compared with

estimated values [8]. With the increasing non-linear loads getting added to the power systems. Standards have been developed to limit the harmonic current injection into the system [9]. From the available literature none of the previous researchers have presented work on designing a k-rated transformer. In this paper a detail design of 250 kVA K-rated transformer and experimental results of total harmonic distortion are presented

II. DESIGN OF 250 KVA K-RATING TRANSFORMER

The flow chart of manufacturing Process of a 250kVA K-rating transformer is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Manufacturing process.

2.1 Design of LV winding

Current per phase is given by $\frac{250 \cdot 1000}{\sqrt{3} \cdot 433} \approx 333.33A$

Consider a conductor of Copper Electrolytic High Conducting half Hardened with current density of $2A/mm^2$ to reduce the load losses. The cross sectional area is given by 166.67 mm^2 ($333.33/2$). Commercially 8mm rod is available and 60% of the area can be utilized [10-11]. Therefore the effective area of each conductor is given by

$$\frac{\pi}{4} \cdot 8^2 \cdot 0.6 \approx 31 \text{mm}^2$$

$$\text{Total no of parallel conductors} = \frac{166.66}{31} \approx 6$$

Assume diameter of core as 170mm, Winding height is twice the diameter of core and is equal to 340mm. Diameter of bare conductor b and radial height h are given by

$$b = \frac{\text{winding height}}{\text{no of turns} \cdot \text{axial parallel conductors}} - 0.4 = \frac{340}{19 \cdot 2} - 0.4 \approx 8.6$$

$$h = \frac{\text{Cross sectional area}}{\text{no of layers} \cdot b} = \frac{166.67}{4 \cdot 8.6} \approx 5$$

size of LV conductor is $8.6 \times 5 \text{ P0.4 } 2Ax \text{ 2R}$, radial depth = 26mm

$$\text{Inner diameter of LV} = \text{core diameter} + 2 \cdot \text{clearance} = 170 + (2 \cdot 3) = 176 \text{mm}$$

$$\text{Outer diameter of LV} = \text{Inner diameter of LV} + (2 \cdot \text{radial depth}) = 176 + (2 \cdot 26) = 228 \text{mm}$$

$$\text{Length of meanturn, } l_{mt} = \left(\frac{ID + OD}{2} \right) \cdot \pi = 0.6346 \text{m}$$

Total length of the conductor = $l_{mt} \cdot \text{no of turns/limb} \cdot \text{no of layers} \cdot \text{no of limbs} \cdot \text{factor} = 0.6346 \cdot 36 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 1.04 = 285.113 \text{m}$

Resistance of LV winding/ph at $75^\circ C$ is given by

$$R = \frac{\rho l}{A} = \frac{0.02128 \cdot 0.6346 \cdot 36}{0.16856} = 2.88 \Omega$$

$$\text{Volume of conductor} = 0.6346 \cdot 36 \cdot 0.16856 = 3.85 \text{ m}^3$$

Considering density of copper as 8.89 gm/cc, the weight of bare conductor/limb = $3.85 \cdot 8.89 \cdot 10^3 = 34.22 \text{kg}$

Weight of conductor for 3 limbs = 102.67 kg

Weight of conductor with Insulation is given by

$$\left(\frac{(9 \cdot 5.4) - (8.6 \cdot 5)}{(8.6 \cdot 5)} \cdot \frac{1}{8.89} + 1 \right) \cdot 102.67 = 104.183 \text{kg}$$

Ordering quantity of conductor by considering factor 1.04 is $104.183 \cdot 1.04 = 109 \text{ kg}$

Stray losses [12] is given by

$$\left\{ \left(\frac{b \cdot \frac{\text{turns}}{\text{layer}} \cdot \text{axial parallel}}{b_i \cdot \frac{\text{turns}}{\text{layer}} \cdot \text{axial parallel}} - 0.4 \right)^4 \cdot \frac{h}{10} \cdot \text{strayloss factor} \right\} \cdot 100$$

$$= \left\{ \left(\frac{8.6 \cdot 18 \cdot 2}{(9 \cdot 18 \cdot 2) - 0.4} \cdot 0.9622 \cdot \frac{5}{10} \right)^4 \cdot \frac{(4)^2 - 0.2}{9} \right\} \cdot 100 = 8.6\%$$

Stray loss for K13 transformer is $8.6 \cdot 13 = 111.91\%$ of load losses.

$$\text{Load losses} = 2.4 \cdot \text{Bare weight} \cdot \text{current density}^2 = 2.4 \cdot 102.6795 \cdot 1.98^2 = 966.1 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Stray losses} = 1.119 \cdot 966.1 = 1081.1 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Total losses} = \text{Load losses} + \text{Stray losses} = 2048 \text{ W}$$

The temperature gradient is given by

$$\frac{\text{Total losses}}{(\text{No of limbs} \cdot \text{no of surfaces} \cdot \text{heat dissipation factor} \cdot \text{winding length} \cdot \text{length of meanturn})} = \frac{2048}{3 \cdot 3 \cdot 60 \cdot 0.34 \cdot 0.6346} = 17.58^\circ C$$

Hot spot temperature is 98°C and in India yearly weighted average ambient temperature is 32°C. Therefore maximum winding temperature is 66°C (98-32). Maximum permissible temperature gradient as per IS2026 is given by

$$\frac{\text{winding temperature} - \text{Top oil temperature}}{1.1} = \frac{66 - 50}{1.1} = 14.54^\circ \text{C}$$

The temperature gradient can be brought down by

1. Reducing losses, which is expensive
2. Increasing the cooling duct by one more duct with four layer-4 axial conductors, 9 conductors/layer.
3. Line the actual part as it is, increase tank surfaces. This is the most economical method.

2.2 Design of LV winding 8.1 × 5.3 P0.4 4A

The formulas used in Section 2.1, will be used to estimate the parameters of LV winding 8.1 × 5.3 P0.4 4A.

Exact cross section of LV winding is given by

$$(8.1 * 5.3 - 0.86) * 4 = 168.28 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$\text{Current density} = 1.981 \text{ A/mm}^2$$

$$\text{Radial depth for 4 layers} = 31 \text{ mm}$$

Using 1mm pressboard around the core and 2mm clearance of LV winding.

$$\text{Inner diameter of LV winding} = 176 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Outer diameter of LV winding} = 238 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Length of the wire} = 292.16 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Resistance of LV/phase at } 75^\circ\text{C} = 2.96 \text{ m}\Omega$$

$$\text{Bare conductor weight for 3 limbs} = 102.678 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Weight of conductor with Insulation} = 104.183 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Ordered quantity} \approx 105 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Stray loss for K13 transformer} = 85\%$$

$$\text{Load losses} = 966.09 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Stray losses} = 1357.65 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Total LV winding losses} = 2324 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Temperature gradient} = 12.97^\circ\text{C}$$

2.3 Design of HV winding 2 × P0.22

Considering LV to HV gap as 24mm and current density as 2.4 A/mm². The parameters of HV winding are estimated by referring to the formulae used in section A.

$$\text{Inner diameter of HV} = 262 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{HV phase current} = 7.57 \text{ A}$$

$$\text{Number of turns per phase} = 1584$$

$$\text{Diameter of the conductor} = 2 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Window height} = 360 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{End clearance of HV winding} = 50 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Winding length} = \text{window height} - \text{end clearance} = 310 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Number of turns per layer} = \frac{310}{2.22} - 1 \approx 138$$

$$\text{Number of layers} = \frac{1584}{138} \approx 12$$

$$\text{HV radial height} = 34 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Length of mean turn} = 929.9 \text{ mm} = 0.9299 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Length of wire} = 4595.6 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Resistance per phase at } 75^\circ\text{C} = 9.98 \Omega$$

$$\text{Bare conductor weight for 3 limbs} = 123.33 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Weight of conductor with Insulation} = 126.54 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Ordered quantity} \approx 127 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Stray loss} = 10.84\%$$

$$\text{Stray loss} = 1.048\%$$

$$\text{Load losses} = 1722 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Stray losses} = 18 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Total HV winding losses} = 1740 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Temperature gradient} = 11.15^\circ\text{C}$$

2.4 Design of Core

By using high grade core material, transformer losses can be minimized and the initial cost can be reduced by making the transformer smaller in size [11]. In the present work 23ZDMH (Laser Scribed CRGO Si Steel 0.23mm thickness) is used as core material. Consider Flux density (B) as 1.5T and transformation ratio (K) of 0.45

$$\text{Volts / turn} = 0.45 * \sqrt{250} = 7.115$$

$$\text{Phase Voltage} = \text{Line voltage} / \sqrt{3} = 433 / \sqrt{3} = 245$$

$$\text{LV Turns} = \text{Phase voltage} / (\text{volts/turn}) = 35.13$$

Consider LV turns as 36 as it is easy to wind even turns and the turns will be symmetrical. Therefore actual volts/turn will be 6.944. The EMF equation of a transformer is given by

$$E = 4.44 Nf BA * 10^{-6}$$

$$\text{Net Area } A = 20852 \text{ mm}^2$$

Considering Packing factor, Stacking factor and Insulation which will consume 10% of the area.

$$\text{Gross Area} = \pi d^2 / 4 = 20852 / 0.9 = 23168 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$\text{Diameter of the core} = 170 \text{ mm}$$

As per IS2026, if the diameter of core is 151mm to 250mm, number of steps provided is 11.

$$\text{Width of 1}^{\text{st}} \text{ core step} = 165 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Stack height} = \sqrt{170^2 - 165^2} \approx 40 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Gross cross section} = 165 * 40 = 6600 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$\text{Net cross section (removing 3% for insulation)}$$

$$= 6600 * 0.97 = 6402 \text{ mm}^2$$

The dimensions of the stepped core is shown in table 2 and the schematic of core is shown in fig. 2.

TABLE 2. Dimensions of stepped core.

Steps	Width (mm)	Stack Height (mm)	Gross Area (mm ²)	Net area (mm ²)	ΣArea (mm ²)
1	165	40	6600	6402	6402
2	155	29	4495	4360	10762
3	145	19	2755	2672	13434
4	135	15	2025	1964	15398
5	125	12	1500	1455	16853
6	115	10	1150	1115	17968
7	100	12	1200	1164	19132
8	85	10	850	824	19956
9	70	7	490	475	20431
10	55	6	330	320	20751
11	35	6	210	203	20954

Fig. 2. Schematic of core.

For net area of 20954 mm², actual flux density = 1.4927T and specific loss for 23ZDMH is 0.5527. The Schematic of the core is shown in fig 2.

Diameter of core = 170mm

Window height, L = 360mm

Centre to center distance, A = 340mm

Total length of the core = 2D + 3L + 4A = 2780mm

Volume of core is given by

Total length of core * Cross sectional of core

= 2780 × 20954 = 58.252 * 10⁶ mm³

Weight of the core is given by

Volume * density of copper

= 58.252 * 7.65 = 445.628 kgs

The build factor owing to joints in the core, number of laminations and type of core will be taken as 15% for transformers upto rating 3MVA.

No load losses is given by

Weight of core * Specific loss * Build factor

= 446 * 0.5527 * 1.15 ≈ 284W

Total load losses is given by

LV winding losses + HV winding losses + Tank losses

= 2324 + 1740 + 250 = 4314 W

Total losses = no load losses + load losses

= 284 + 4314 = 4598W

2.5 Efficiency of Transformer

Efficiency of a transformer is given by

$$\eta = \frac{\text{output}}{\text{output} + \text{losses}} = \frac{250000}{250000 + 4598} * 100 = 98.2\%$$

Load at which maximum efficiency occurs is given by

$$\sqrt{\frac{\text{No load loss}}{\text{Total losses}}} = \sqrt{\frac{284}{4598}} * 100 = 24.85\%$$

Maximum efficiency η_m of a transformer occurs when no load losses is equal to load losses and is given by

$$= \frac{250000 * 0.2485}{(250000 * 0.2485) + 284 + 284} * 100 = 99.1\%$$

2.6 Regulation of Transformer

Impedance at 75°C is estimated as

$$e_k = \sqrt{e_r^2 + e_x^2}$$

The load loss/capacity [12] e_r is given by

$$e_r = \frac{\text{load loss}}{\text{capacity}} = \frac{4314}{250000} * 100 = 1.72\%$$

$$e_x = \frac{1.24 * H * \Delta' D_s * 10^{-4}}{(\text{volts / turn}) * I_s}$$

H = ampere turns = 12000 AT

Δ = bare conductor gap between LV and HV = 12.31mm

h_2 = effective radial height of HV = 32.975mm

h_1 = effective radial height of LV = 28.9mm

$$\Delta' = \Delta + \frac{1}{3}(h_1 + h_2) = 32.935\text{mm}$$

$$D_s = (\text{OD of LV} - 0.4) + \Delta + \frac{1}{3}(h_2 - h_1) = 251.27\text{mm}$$

$$l = \frac{(\text{LV length} - \text{insulation}) + (\text{HV length} - \text{insulation})}{2}$$

$$l = \frac{(340 - 0.4) + (310 - 0.22)}{2} = 324.69$$

$$b = \frac{(\text{OD of HV} - \text{insulation}) - (\text{ID of LV} - \text{insulation})}{2}$$

$$b = \frac{(330 - 0.22) - (176 - 0.4)}{2} = 77.09$$

$$\text{Rogowski factor } K_r = 1 - \frac{\left(1 - e^{-\frac{\pi l}{b}}\right)}{\left(\frac{\pi l}{b}\right)} = 0.9244$$

$$I_s = \frac{l}{K_r} = \frac{324.69}{0.9244} = 351.23$$

$$e_x = \frac{1.24 * 12000 * 32.935 * 251.27 * 10^{-4}}{6.9442 * 351.23} = 5.05\%$$

$$e_k = \sqrt{1.75^2 + 5.05^2} = 5.344\%$$

$$\text{Regulation} = e_r + \frac{e_x^2}{200} = 1.88\%$$

2.7 Design of Transformer Tank

Tank length = 2A + HV OD + LV clearance

$$= (2 * 340) + 330 + 50 = 1060\text{mm} = 10.6\text{dm}$$

Tank width = LV clearance + HVOD + HV clearance

$$= 25 + 330 + 50 = 405\text{mm} = 4.05\text{dm}$$

Tank height = core foot + core height + window height + yoke height + clearance of oil

$$= 10 + (165 * 2) + 360 + 60 = 760\text{mm} = 7.6\text{dm}$$

Volume of tank = 10.6 * 4.05 * 7.6 = 326.26dm³ ≈ 327 litres

Displacement of oil due to core is given by

$$\frac{\text{weight of core}}{\text{Density}} = \frac{446}{7.65} = 58.3\text{litres}$$

Displacement of oil due to winding is given by

$$\frac{\text{weight of winding}}{\text{Density}} = \frac{232}{8.89} = 26.1\text{litres}$$

Displacement of oil due to insulation = 20 litres
 Displacement of oil due to mild steel (core bolts, tie rods, channels) is given by

$$\frac{\text{weight of mild steel}}{\text{Density}} = \frac{80}{7.85} = 10.2 \text{ litres}$$

Total displacement of oil due to active parts of transformer is given by

$$58.3 + 26.1 + 20 + 10.2 \approx 115 \text{ litres}$$

$$\text{Volume of oil in the tank} = 327 - 115 = 212 \text{ litres}$$

Total surface area of four sides of transformer is given by

$$((1.06 * 0.76) + (0.405 * 0.76)) * 2 = 2.2268 \text{ m}^2$$

Heat dissipation by surface wall is 500W/m²

$$\text{Therefore heat dissipation} = 2.2268 * 500 \approx 1114 \text{ W}$$

Heat dissipation factor is given by

$$\left(\frac{\text{winding temperature}}{\text{top oil temperature}} \right)^{1/0.7} = \left(\frac{55}{50} \right)^{1/0.7} = 1.146$$

Total heat to be dissipated is given by

$$(\text{Heat dissipation factor} * (\text{No load losses} + \text{hot spot coefficient} * (\text{LV losses} + \text{HV losses} + \text{tank losses})))$$

$$= 1.146 * (284 + (1.1 * 4314)) = 5764 \text{ W}$$

Heat to be dissipated by radiators is given by

$$\text{Total heat- heat dissipation by transformer walls}$$

$$= 5764 - 1114 = 4650 \text{ W}$$

For top oil of 50°C radiator dissipation factor is 450W/m²

$$\text{Area of radiators} = \frac{4650}{450} = 10.4 \text{ m}^2$$

Height of radiator is given by

$$\text{tank height} - \text{top clearance} - \text{bottom clearance} = 760 - 90 - 180 = 500 \text{ mm} = 0.5 \text{ m}$$

Width of radiator = 0.3m

$$\text{Surface area/fin} = (0.5 * 0.3) * 2 = 0.3 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\text{Total number of fins} = \frac{\text{total area}}{\text{surface area}} = \frac{10.4}{0.3} \approx 36$$

Use 4 radiator sets with 9 fins per radiator

Oil per fin including header = 1.55 litre

Weight per fin = 3.25 kg

$$\text{Total weight of fins} = 36 * 3.25 = 117 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Total oil in radiators} = 36 * 1.55 = 56 \text{ litres}$$

$$\text{Oil in tank and radiators} = 212 + 56 = 268 \approx 270 \text{ litres}$$

Expansion of transformer oil is given by

$$\text{total oil} * \text{coefficient of expansion} * \text{raise in temperature} = 270 * 0.00078 * 75 = 15.795 \approx 15.8 \text{ litres}$$

oil in the conservator is 4% of transformer tank oil

$$= 270 * 0.04 = 10.8 \text{ litres}$$

Therefore total oil required = 270 + 10.8 ≈ 281 litres

Weight of transformer oil = volume * density

$$= 281 * 0.889 \approx 250 \text{ kgs}$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Harmonic analysis test was conducted on a 250 kVA transformer and the test set up is shown in fig. 3. The voltage and current waveforms is shown in fig. 4. The total harmonic distortion in voltage and current waveform with amplitude is shown in fig. 5 and fig. 6 respectively. It is observed that from fig. 4 there is no much distortion in the voltage waveform

shape, whereas there is more distortion in current waveform i.e. not in pure sinusoidal wave shape. The total harmonic distortion (THD) is measured in both voltage and current waveforms. The amplitude of THD in voltage and current waveform is 2.2% and 4.8% respectively. These values are well within the limits specified by the standards [9] and hence validates the designed values.

Fig. 3. Test set up for performing Harmonic analysis.

Fig. 4. Voltage and current waveforms.

Fig. 5. Voltage waveform.

Fig. 6. Current waveform and THD amplitude.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a detailed design of a 250 kVA rating transformer is presented. The estimated losses, efficiency and regulation were well within the limits as per standards. Total Harmonic distortion in the current waveform was found to be more than voltage waveform and the amplitude was 4.8% and 2.2% respectively. Using this K-rating transformer the life of the transformer can be increased. The designed 250 kVA K-rated transformer is capable of meeting any level of non-linear load without raising the temperature and not leading to any negative consequences. By installing the k-rating transformers at all the non-linear load centers the distribution losses can be reduced to considerable extent. Even though the initial cost is high compared to conventional transformer, the payback period is less than 12 years and leads to lot of saving of money to the utility companies.

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